

Solvent effect and Mechanism of the Base Hydrolysis of Ethyl Acetoacetate

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The hydrolysis of acetoacetic ester in presence of 0.019*N* sodium hydroxide has been carried out in dioxane-water and acetone-water medium at different temperatures under iso-dielectric conditions. The role of water and its possible "order" in the hydrolysis has been sought to be explained within the framework of the conventionally accepted mechanisms of the ester hydrolysis. It has been shown that the kinetics involves "mixed order processes". The variation of the dielectric constant of the medium has been special importance in the revelation of the order.

Experimental

ETHYL acetoacetate—Distilled acid free ethyl acetoacetate (G.R.E. Merck) was used in the investigations.

Acetone was purified by a standard procedure¹. Dioxane was made acid free and distilled before use.

Isodielectric media consisting of different solvent pairs such as dioxane-water and acetone-water at different temperatures were made by the procedure reported earlier^{2,2a, 2b}.

The kinetic study involved the method of titration. The experiment was conducted in an electrically operated water bath which maintained constant temperature within $\pm 0.1^\circ$. Equal volumes of ester

attain the temperature of the bath. Experimental solutions were then mixed up and 10 ml portions of the mixture titrated against standard alkali at different time intervals.

Results and Discussion

The hydrolysis process follows an overall second order rate law. The measurements at different temperatures were made under isodielectric condition to ensure the same macroelectrical environment during the formation of the transition state³. The logarithm of the measured rate constant in dioxane-water medium is plotted against the reciprocal of the dielectric constant. It is observed that the graphs (Fig. 1) are partly linear and departures from linearity

Fig. 1. (A) → 25°
(B) → 30°
(C) → 35°
(D) → 40°
(E) → 45°

Fig. 2. (A) → 10°
(B) → 20°
(C) → 25°
(D) → 30°
(E) → 35°

(0.019 *M*) and sodium hydroxide (0.019 *M*) solutions were placed in the thermostat for about an hour to

do occur when the aqueous component of the solvent media falls below certain values. When the water

component of the binary medium (dioxane-water) reaches a concentration around 40 to 45 gm. moles per litre, the point of departure from linearity is reached. For acetone-water binary, however, the departures from linearity take place at about water concentration 29 to 47 gm. mole per litre (depending on temperature) (Fig. 2).

In both the cases, deviating points have been purposely drawn on a second straight line (contrary to conventional curved tails) resulting in a break for each temperature. This has been done with a view to bring out the similarities between these sets of curves and the corresponding curves of k_{obs} Vs the concentration of water in the binary (Figs. 3 and 4). The latter curves also display breaks at about the same concentration of water as in the dielectric constant curves. Incidentally, we have tested quite a number of k_{obs} and $\frac{1}{D}$ data obtained by different authors⁴⁻⁷ in different kinetic experiments. The experimental points can be accommodated, more or less, on two interesting straight lines. This strengthens and supports the mode of representation of $\log k_{obs}$ Vs. $\frac{1}{D}$ as described in the foregoing paragraph.

Fig. 3. (A) \rightarrow 25°
(B) \rightarrow 30°
(C) \rightarrow 35°
(D) \rightarrow 40°
(E) \rightarrow 45°

The interpretations sometimes ascribed to such cases of deviations from linearity in the plots of $\log k_{obs}$ Vs $\frac{1}{D}$ are changes in mechanisms of the reaction with variation of the solvent component^{8,9} or to preferential solvation^{7,7a} (solvent sorting) by the higher dielectric component of the binary.

Instances also exist where departures from linearity occur in the $\log k_{obs}$ Vs $\frac{1}{D}$ curves when the water

content in the organo-aqueous binary is rather high. These have been attributed to specific solvent effect and results from partial breakdown of the water structure in the alkaline hydrolysis of acetyl mandalate ion in ethylene-glycol water mixtures⁷.

The above instances, amongst others, point to the inadequacies of the overall dielectric constant alone in the interpretation of the rate phenomena and incidentally hint at the increasing importance of the aqueous content in kinetic processes. In our investigations, since macro electrical surroundings were sought to be ensured through maintenance of isodielectric media, the importance of solvent composition takes on an additional weightage.

It will be apt for us if we seek to elucidate the mechanism of hydrolysis of acetoacetic ester within the framework of the known and established mechanisms of the hydrolysis. Experiments have been performed on the basic hydrolysis of ethyl acetoacetate¹⁰ and basic hydrolysis of α : α -dialkyl substituted ethyl acetoacetate in water medium by Pedersen¹¹. The rates of ketonic decomposition of the free acetoacetic acid, of the corresponding dialkyl substituted acid and of their anions were also measured by Pedersen^{11,12,13} by observing the decarboxylation rate. Through a long series of comparative measurement,

Fig. 4. (A) \rightarrow 10°
(B) \rightarrow 20°
(C) \rightarrow 25°
(D) \rightarrow 30°
(E) \rightarrow 35°

the conclusion was drawn by Pedersen, that in these decarboxylation and hydrolytic processes the ester, the acid (free or substituted) and anions of the acid react in the keto form. We shall proceed with our deliberations and treatment of the results with the acceptance of this view point.

A number of trial plots of k_{obs} Vs $[H_2O]^n$ with varying n have been made. These plots with values of $n \neq 1$ do not show any specific regularity; but the plots with $n = 1$ comprise two straight lines meeting each other.

An adherence to the common hydrolytic mechanism would demand the bimolecular acyl oxygen scission to be operative in aceto-acetic ester hydrolysis. The mechanism as is well known¹⁴⁻¹⁷ consists of a nucleophilic attack by hydroxyl group on the carbonyl carbon and an electrophilic attack of water molecule on the ether oxygen.

In the above mechanism the attack by water molecule takes place at a stage subsequent to the hydroxyl addition. Laidler and Landskroener¹⁸, however, presume a simultaneous attack on the ester molecule by both the hydroxyl group and water molecule in the general scheme.

In our case if we assume two distinct stages for hydroxyl addition and water attack for rising part of the curves, and supplement it with a further assumption that the fixation of H₂O with the ester hydroxide adduct is the slowest step, then it follows

$$\begin{aligned} k_{obs}[\text{OH}^-][\text{ester}] &= k[\text{adduct}][\text{H}_2\text{O}] \\ &= kK[\text{OH}^-][\text{ester}][\text{H}_2\text{O}] \\ &= k'[\text{OH}^-][\text{ester}][\text{H}_2\text{O}] \\ \therefore k_{obs} &= k'[\text{H}_2\text{O}] \quad \dots (1) \end{aligned}$$

The concentration of the adduct, which is in equilibrium with the reactant molecules, is expressed in terms of the concentrations of the reactants and the corresponding equilibrium constant *K*. The observed rate constant thus becomes linearly dependent on the concentration of water (equation 1).

The hydrolytic mechanism of simultaneous additions¹⁹ of OH⁻ and H₂O is possibly operative for the remaining parts of the said curves i.e., for portions prior to breaks, (i.e. water concentration 40 to 45 gm. moles/litre approximately).

The observed rate constant would then depend as is experimentally found, on the concentration of water.

$$v = k''[\text{ester}][\text{OH}^-][\text{H}_2\text{O}] \quad \dots (2)$$

It should be mentioned that in the dioxane-rich composition, the simultaneous incursion by OH⁻ and H₂O on the ester molecule is not the sole mechanism operative. It may be noted that the lines (Fig. 3) extrapolated to zero concentration of water show intercepts which indicate contributions towards *k*_{obs} by a "true second order bimolecular process" in which the rate determining step is independent of water participation. We can state, therefore, that the hydrolysis of acetoacetic ester in dioxane-water medium proceeds by a mixed mechanism via "true second order bimolecular process" and an "apparent second order termolecular process" up to water concentration of 40 or so gm. moles per litre (prior to breaks, Fig. 3). The observed rate constant for this region can, therefore, be written as

$$k_{obs} = k_1 + k_2[\text{H}_2\text{O}] \quad \dots (3)$$

suggesting a linear dependence on water. For water concentration shooting beyond 40 to 47 gm. moles/litre (depending on the temperature) in the solvent-pair, the rate determining process becomes a bimolecular one with an apparent second order dependence on ester and hydroxyl concentration (i.e., an apparent first order dependence on the adduct concentration) (eq. 1).

We summarise our conclusions regarding the mechanism and the role of water in it in the form of the following two schemes.

Scheme 1 (valid upto breaks in curves shown in Fig. 3). Simultaneous occurrence of (i) True second order bimolecular mechanism and (ii) Apparent second order termolecular mechanism.

Scheme 2 (valid for portions beyond the breaks in curves shown in Fig. 3).

Apparent second order bimolecular mechanism.

A possible limitation linked up with the extrapolation of *k*_{obs} curve to zero concentration of water (Figs. 3 and 4) can arise only if the kinetic behaviour of the system in dioxane-water medium is very much different in the range of dielectric constant values below and above 12, the lowest value experimentally employed. Provided that such an extrapolation is permitted, one can draw up a table 1 below showing the percentage of the kinetics proceeding via true second order bimolecular mechanism characterised by the rate constant *k*₁ and an apparently second order termolecular mechanism characterised by *k*₂[H₂O] of equation (3).

It should be remarked that if such an extrapolation be not valid due to interception of physical factors (such as ion association²⁰) below dielectric constant 12, the hypothetical intercept that is obtained by actual extrapolation can be meaningfully used at least for the domain of dielectric constant 12 to 49.5 (approx.). In other words, the break-up of the kinetic data shown in the foregoing table is at least valid for this span of the dielectric constant of the mixed solvent medium (dioxane-water).

Attention may now be turned to Fig. 4, which depicts the dependence of rate constant of the hydrolysis of acetoacetic ester on the concentration of water in acetone-water medium.

The curves are similar to those observed in case of dioxane-water medium except in some qualitative aspects. Here the following features may be noted.

(i) For most of the temperatures studied, almost all the experimental points obtained over a range of dielectric constant 31.5 to 69.5 (approx.) are accommodated on a straight line.

(ii) The kinetic rate constant values for pure water medium sharply deviate from the previous straight line under (i) except for 10° curve.

(iii) The deviating tendency becomes less and less as the temperature is lowered until at 10°, all the points (from dielectric constant 31.5 to that of pure water) lie on a single straight line.

TABLE 1. BASE HYDROLYSIS OF ACETOACETIC ESTER. (WATER-DIOXANE MEDIUM). VALUES OF THE SPLIT RATE CONSTANT

Temp. °C	Dielectric constant	Molar conc. of water	k_1 lit mole ⁻¹ min ⁻¹	$k_2 \times 10^2$ lit mole ⁻¹ min ⁻¹	k_1'	k_2'	Percentage of reaction Proceeding by	
							True sec. order bi-mole.mech.	App. sec. order termol. mechanism
25	62.5	45.73	0.20	3.0	0.20	1.37	12.73	87.27
	49.5	37.94	"	"	"	1.04	16.14	83.86
	36.0	29.63	"	"	"	0.89	18.30	81.70
	12.0	13.85	"	"	"	0.41	32.52	67.48
30	49.5	38.70	0.7	3.66	0.7	1.42	33.02	66.98
	36.0	30.40	"	"	"	1.11	38.61	61.39
	12.0	14.37	"	"	"	0.53	57.10	42.90
35	49.5	39.49	1.1	3.60	1.1	1.42	43.65	56.35
	36.0	30.91	"	"	"	1.11	49.77	50.23
	12.0	14.63	"	"	"	0.52	67.69	32.31
40	49.5	40.23	1.25	5.0	1.25	2.01	38.33	61.67
	36.0	31.70	"	"	"	1.58	44.09	55.91
	12.0	14.88	"	"	"	0.74	62.70	37.30
45	36.0	31.90	1.8	5.14	1.8	1.64	52.32	47.68
	12.0	15.12	"	"	"	0.78	69.88	30.12

TABLE 2. BASE HYDROLYSIS OF ACETOACETIC ESTER IN ACETONE-WATER MEDIUM. VALUES OF THE SPLIT RATE CONSTANTS

Temp. °C	Dielectric constant	Molar conc. of water	k_1 lit mole ⁻¹ min ⁻¹	k_2 lit mole ⁻¹ min ⁻¹	k_1'	k_2'	Percentage of reaction Proceeding by	
							True sec. order bi-mole.mech.	App. sec. order termole mechanism
10	Pure water	55.00	0.16	0.018	0.16	1.00	13.8	86.2
	69.5	39.96	"	"	"	0.72	18.2	81.8
	58.0	29.69	"	"	"	0.53	23.05	76.95
	45.5	19.42	"	"	"	0.35	31.43	68.57
	31.5	8.87	"	"	"	0.16	50.15	49.85
20	58.0	32.71	0.36	0.021	0.36	0.69	34.10	65.90
	45.5	21.62	"	"	"	0.46	43.90	56.10
	31.5	10.53	"	"	"	0.22	61.65	38.35
25	58.0	33.52	0.62	0.024	0.62	0.81	53.07	46.93
	45.5	22.53	"	"	"	0.54	62.81	37.19
	31.5	11.08	"	"	"	0.27	77.45	22.55
30	58.0	35.27	0.98	0.034	0.98	1.21	44.75	55.25
	45.5	23.77	"	"	"	0.81	54.59	45.41
	31.5	11.88	"	"	"	0.41	70.65	29.35
35	58.0	37.00	1.04	0.045	1.04	1.65	38.66	61.34
	45.5	24.58	"	"	"	1.10	48.60	51.40
	31.5	12.42	"	"	"	0.56	65.12	34.88

The mechanistic interpretation, keeping in view the variation of k_{obs} vis-a-vis water concentration in acetone-water medium is similar to the one given for dioxane-water medium.

Considering the intercepts made with k_{obs} axis (Fig. 4) the mechanism consists of

(1) Simultaneous prevalence of a "true second order bimolecular process" and an "apparent second order termolecular process" represented by a rate constant expression

$$k_{obs} = k_1 + k_2[\text{H}_2\text{O}] \quad \dots (4)$$

for the dielectric constant range 31.5 to 69.5 (maximum water concentration 45 gm. moles per litre).

(2) For water-rich solvent medium a rate determining bimolecular process with involvement of water showing an apparent second order dependence on ester and hydroxyl ion.

A table 2 is, therefore drawn up for the present case, like the one (Table 1) given for dioxane-water

medium, demonstrating the break-up of the kinetic data based on the suggested mechanism.

A previous study on the acid hydrolysis of an α -keto ester in different binary media showed mixed order processes occurring simultaneously during hydrolysis. In the present instance, a β -keto ester also seems to follow the trend.

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